

STUDIES IN SCURVY

BY

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To

Professors Axel Holst and Theodor Frölich

This work is respectfully inscribed by

THE AUTHOR

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Preface.

The work which is here presented was begun in July, 1922. It would have been impracticable to fulfil it without the possibilities of technical aid offered by clinical laboratories. To Professors F. HENSCHEN and G. HÄGGQUIST, who have allowed me to avail myself of these possibilities and to whom I am also indebted for much helpful advice, I beg to express my gratitude. My thanks are also due to Professors I. JUNDELL and U. QUENSEL, to Assistant Professor Dr. C. KLING, Doctors R. NORDGREN, G. VESTBECK, H. DAVIDE, A. WASSÉN, S. SIVE, A. WALLGREN, Å. ÅKERLUND, the Dental Surgeon Dr. G. WESTIN, and others, for various reasons, some of which I have mentioned more particularly in my book. Special thanks are due to Doctor F. WAHLGREN and Fil. Doctor L. G. ROMELL who have kindly read the proofs.

My late father, the historian NILS J. HÖJER, who during all his life, beside his practical activity as a teacher, devoted himself to scientific work for science's sake, has been my model. My wife, SIGNE HÖJER, has been my helper.

I have allowed myself as a respectful token of admiration to inscribe my work to Professors AXEL HOLST and THEODOR FRÖLICH in Christiania, the first investigators in the field of experimental scurvy, whose work still remains unrivalled. Even though the exaggeration is evident in Funk's utterance (1922): »Since the experiments of Holst and Frölich, no real progress has been made (in experimental scurvy), in spite of the numerous publications that have appeared», yet his words show how high Holst and Frölich's works rank among all the rest.

Hagalund, Sweden. February 1924.

J. Axel Höjer.

the formation of elongated fibrils has failed. Before the formation of collagen is completely arrested, there is thus a stage when it is very unevenly distributed and irregularly arranged.

It is related by several early authors that old bone fractures at the onset of scurvy have become softened. The deficient callus-formation at fractures in scorbutically changed bones is also a common observation in the study of experimental scurvy. Also for the explanation of these circumstances, the pronounced atrophy of the collagen connective tissue in scurvy is of interest. Even if, as CARRELL has pointed out in experiments (1921), the cicatrization of wounds apparently is initiated not by an internal but by an external factor, the answer of the organism to the irritation is decided by internal factors. That a supply of full antiscorbutic dose is necessary to an answer of normal intensity, may be concluded from this investigation.

A general insufficiency in the collagen formation is not, as far as I know, earlier described.

PART III.

CHAPTER I.

Scurvy and infection.

I. Complicating acute infections in my animals.

Of my 189 animals about a third (60) have suffered from complicating acute infection. In the majority of cases it has been an acute infection of the upper respiratory canal. Pneumonia has been found in 13 animals, enterocolitis in 5, septico-pyemia in 8, peritonitis in 1, necrosis of pancreas in 1. No wide-spread epidemic has occurred. As remarkable may be mentioned the appearance of pneumonia in 4 of the 8 animals in Series 34. In Series 29 two animals showed abscesses in the spleen.

It may be mentioned that I have not in any case found any coccidiosis. The liver was examined in nearly all cases.

II. Influence of acute infection on scurvy.

Since the hypothesis of scurvy as being an infectious disease has more and more had to yield to the vitamin hypothesis, attempts have been made to represent the infection as a necessary factor for bringing about manifest symptoms in an organism changed through lack of antiscorbutic. The reasons for these attempts are the same circumstances that caused the supposition of an altogether infectious etiology: 1) the »endemic» occurrence in certain cases, 2) the presence of acute infections in connection with the onset of the disease, and 3) the so-called scurvy fever. With regard to these circumstances the following observations may be made.

Ad 1). The endemic occurrence in persons with identical or similar dietary is more satisfactorily explained by the vitamin hypothesis.

Ad 2). That certain acute infections may have an influence on the arising and course of scurvy, is certain. ASCHOFF and KOCH state that every powerful infection in a patient with old scurvy calls forth new hemorrhages. SALLE and ROSENBERG mention that dysentery, typhoid and malaria aggravate the scurvy. Yet they have only a small number of such cases at their disposal. BIERICH saw in his large material a predisposing influence only of abdominal typhoid and dysentery, but not of tuberculosis, lues, polyarthritis acuta, or malaria. This action of diarrhea diseases has already in 1907 been observed by HOLST and FRÖLICH. »Diarrhea creates very often a predisposition to scurvy».

Several authors could verify this during the last war, and HESS dwells in 1920 specially on this fact. Concerning infants the same thing has been observed by, among others, VOGT and WALLGREN. LEICHTENTRITT and ZIELASKOWSKI write in 1922, that »chronische Darmerkrankungen — gleichgültig ob infektiöser, alimentärer, konstitutioneller Grundlage — dem Scorbut

die Wege eben und infolgedessen geradezu als 'Barlow-trop' aufzufassen sind». It is near at hand to connect this circumstance with an action in the intestinal canal on the antiscorbutic from abnormal products (oxidizing?).

Concerning other infections there are no certain observations in a positive direction recorded in the literature. Two of my guinea-pigs, No. 50 and 55, see charts Fig. 105 and 106, pp. 186, 188, are examples of how scurvy seems to proceed in the manner determined by the food, independently of an intercurrent acute infection. Such an infection seems in these cases to have caused a decrease in weight, which gives to the curves of these animals a course different from those of the other animals in the same series. The decrease yields place to an increase, however, and it is then found that the curves go rising towards those of the other animals, and bend downwards with these, as the animals also proceed to death at the same time as their fellows.

The influence of certain acute infections on the onset and progress of scurvy can thus be limited, partly to diseases that bring about intestinal disturbances, in which a direct action on the antiscorbutic before its resorption will easily be concluded, partly to causing hemorrhages in certain cases of already scorbutic patients. It does not seem surprising, with the already described weakness in the vascular walls, more particularly explained by me, that a hyperemia and thereby raised demands should call forth a hemorrhage. This may also be caused by other incidental circumstances, for instance trauma, or set in without any demonstrable cause.

Ad 3). The scurvy fever has always at closer analysis showed itself explainable either as a resorption fever in connection with a hemorrhage (FINKELSTEIN), or as a consequence of a complicating infection, whereas the scurvy as such proceeds without fever, which has also been stated experimentally (JACKSON and MOORE).

In the case of my guinea-pigs I have not taken the temperature, and I have as a rule made no cultures of bacteria. Clinically, at the *post-mortem* and the subsequent histological

examination, an infection was stated in 22 out of 86 animals with manifest scurvy. Thus, in nearly 75 per cent. of the cases with manifest scurvy no signs of infection could be found. On the other hand, more than half the number of animals that had latent scurvy, suffered from an infection, without manifest symptoms being called forth through this circumstance.

As a result of this it may be emphasized that there are no sufficient reasons for ABELS' hypothesis, quoted above, about an infection being necessary for the scorbutic symptoms to become manifest. The circumstances which are the foundation of Abels' hypothesis might instead be expressed thus, that scurvy in man often has not had time to become manifest before an infection comes on as a consequence of the immunity being lowered by the scurvy. If, like Abels, one wishes to call the lessened resistance of the body to infections by the name of dysergy, this is quite as legitimate as many other attempts to conceal with a fine name that a thing is still incompletely investigated. To establish the dysergy as a latent stage, distinct from the manifest, is in any case unwarranted.

Thus infection in scurvy is generally to be regarded as a concomitant symptom as well as the hemorrhage. These two show besides many analogies.

1. They may both be regarded as following the scorbutic atrophy, *viz.*, the atrophy of the vessels and of the various organs that protect the body against infections.

2. Both appear in the later stages of scurvy spontaneously, the hemorrhages after physiological action, for instance contraction of the muscles, the infection without any contagion being possible to state. In an earlier stage of the disease, however, a greater injury is needed, either a violence that leads to hemorrhage, or a pathogenic bacterium that gives rise to infection.

3. Both may aggravate the scurvy symptoms, the hemorrhage by causing necroses, *e. g.*, in the musculature, the infection by acting upon the antiscorbutic in the intestine. They may also mutually educe each other, the hemorrhage becoming a *locus*

minoris resistentiae, that becomes purulent, the hyperemia, called forth by the infection, causing hemorrhages from the weakened vessels.

4. To both, though ordinarily only concomitant symptoms of scurvy, a decisive influence on the genesis of the scurvy has been attached. The hemorrhages have been considered (BARLOW, LOOSER a. o.) to call forth all other changes; earlier, the infection has generally been considered as representing the whole etiology, and lately (ABELS) as being necessary for the passing of scurvy from a latent to a manifest stage.

III. Influence of scurvy on immunity and resistance against infection.

The numerous statements in this question are summarized in 1920 by HESS in the following way:

»The latent scurvy increases the susceptibility to infection and intensifies the severity of all medical and surgical diseases.» — »Indeed, one of the striking and important symptoms of scurvy is the marked susceptibility to infections (furunculosis, nasal diphtheria, grippe, bronchitis, pneumonia). Pneumonia is one of the most frequent complications and causes of death. This susceptibility was noted by the elder authors in relation to adults. — Following the infection, the lymphnodes may become purulent, as is so frequently mentioned by the elder authors.»

»Der scorbutische Organismus», write LEICHTENTRITT and ZIELASKOWSKI in 1922, »ist nicht imstande, auf bakterielle Einwirkungen Abwehrreaktionen aufzubringen. Als Ausdruck dafür sind die kaum zur Heilung zu bringenden Furunculosen und torpiden Hautgeschwüre mit ihrer schlechten Neigung zur Granulationsbildung anzusehen.» According to KOCH this is a current observation, quoted by many elder authors. NASSAU and SINGER emphasize how in scurvy there is seen as well a lowering of the immunity with more frequent infections, as a diminished resistance with a more malignant progress of infections. For this Abels has invented the word *dysergy*.

With regard to the number of the acute infections in my material, the following figures may be quoted.

Of the 62 animals, that I had put on absolute scorbutic dietary, basal diet without any antiscorbutic (scorbut gravior), 18 (29 %) showed signs of acute infection. Of the 72 animals, that had a certain, but not sufficient dose of antiscorbutic (scorbut mitior), 34 (47 %) showed such signs. The corresponding figures for the animals on complete diet are 9 out of 45 (20 %). In judging of these figures we must consider the essentially different lifetime, which for animals with scorbut mitior is twice, and for those on complete dietary three times that of the animals on absolute scorbutic dietary.

Of the groups that had 0.5—0.8 of the minimum protective dose and thus a scurvy which still at the conclusion of the experiment after 92 days was latent, in all 24 animals, only 8 were alive at the end of the experiment. Of the others, 13 (54.2 %) had died with signs of acute infections. Of 40 animals that had had complete dietary, 29 were alive and in good health after the same length of time. 8 had died of acute infection and 1 had pneumonia when killed (in all 22.5 %). The animals that had latent scurvy thus showed about twice as many infections leading to death than those on complete dietary.

With regard to all figures here quoted it may be said, that they are not founded on a uniform material, as the animals were kept in 12 different cages and thus were exposed to different infections. This remark is just and renders it impossible to divide the animals into smaller groups or to attach too much importance to the figures quoted. They might, however, authorize the conclusion, that the increased disposition for being afflicted by infectious diseases, which has earlier been noted in scorbutic patients already in the latent stage, is apparent also in my material.

The infections in Series 33 and 34, that had 1.2 and 1.6, respectively, of the calculated minimum protective dose, give occasion to a remark. Of 8 animals in each group, 2 died of acute infection in the first, 4 in the second. Here we might

advance the supposition that, though no patho-anatomical changes in these animals are found that might imply scurvy, except an uncertain hyperemia in the tooth pulp, yet the dose of antiscorbutic would not be fully protective. If so, there would exist an initial stage of scurvy, where no distinct histological atrophy, only a functional weakness in the highest developed cells would be present. The infections in question might be an expression of such a weakness. This possibility is not to be excluded. In guinea-pigs with scorbut gravior the first week probably is such a stage. With regard to the parallelism of the stages, such as they are seen in scorbut gravior from the onset till the manifest symptoms appear, with those stages that are called forth by giving different, smaller and smaller doses of antiscorbutic from the beginning, such a stage may even with probability be expected, if a dose is given which is barely sufficient to ward off the histological changes. The difference between this dose and one which assures full vigour from an antiscorbutic point of view, will be made clear by physiological investigations. Such a stage ought appropriately to be called *scorbut initialis* or *functional scurvy*.

The investigations which have aimed at finding the cause of the lessened resistance in the scorbutic organism against infections, are few. ZILVA examined in scorbutic guinea-pigs the amboceptor and agglutinin titers of the blood and the complement activity; he found these unchanged. This does not exclude, however, that, as is the case with the number of blood cells, a raised demand reveals a weakness in the regenerative power. FORTENATO found in 1921 the opsonic index lowered in scorbutic guinea-pigs. LEICHTENTRITT and ZIELASKOWSKI examined the trypanocid substance of the blood in scurvy and found it lessened. Their experiments are too few in number to allow any sure conclusions to be drawn. I have not undertaken any corresponding investigations. In this connection, however, I may recall the result of the histological examination of the lymphoid tissue in my cases of scurvy, complicated by acute infection, as far as it has been examined. (See page 93, 94).

It seems we may conclude from this that the lymphoid tissue in scurvy reacts tardily to infections. In this atrophical state of the lymphoid tissue as well as in the changes of the bone-marrow we may have to seek one foundation for the inferiority of the scorbut organism in the struggle against infections.

CHAPTER II.

Disposition and scurvy.

That different rapidity of growth, thus also different ages, dispose differently to scurvy is established and founded on the very nature of the disease. The »disposition» to scurvy which is found in individuals with intestinal disturbances, may be explained as due to an external factor — probably destroying of antiscorbutic in the intestine.

Apart from these two circumstances we know nothing with certainty about the disposition to scurvy in different persons. Many authors have presumed such a disposition, it is true, but they seem to forget that the diagnosis in this case is a diagnosis of elimination, and that among the external factors that are to be excluded, are the following: the age of the food (milk) before it is consumed, the preparation of food in the kitchen, a careful determination of the quantities consumed of the substances that may contain antiscorbutic, control of the nurse.

FINKELSTEIN's oft-quoted case (a pair of twins) does not fulfil these claims. Another account of the same author of how 3 children with the same nurse had scurvy one after the other, whereas no other children in the department had the disease, without the external factor, which nevertheless must be supposed to have existed, being discovered, invites to caution. Nor do we learn with regard to WIELAND's twins, of which one had scurvy and the other not, which quantities they each of them consumed. But in the absence of an exact statement about this the explanation may be thought to be the same as has been given by CHICK and HUME of the state-

ment of McCOLLUM, PITZ etc. which were at variance with the results of other authors. The American investigators had not observed that the guinea-pigs took unequal quantities of raw milk, which contained a certain amount of antiscorbutic. Some of them had scurvy, while those who took sufficiently were protected.

Another example of a precipitate conclusion with regard to a disposition (psychical) is given in BIERICH'S description of a number of scurvy patients who appeared greatly depressed in the hospital. When they had been removed to a forest sanatorium, where they were allowed to cultivate and harvest their own vegetables, both their spirits and the scurvy improved. Bierich thinks, as so many older authors have thought, the better spirits to be the probable cause of the recovery. It is likely, however, that also the vegetables in the forest sanatorium were better from the antiscorbutic point of view. Bierich has made an excellent exposition of his large material, but it gives him no right to the conclusion he draws from it, whether his supposition of the psychical influence may be or may not be found correct.

Conclusion.

Irrespective of the cases which are connected with an unequal rapidity of growth, and those connected with intestinal disturbances, no endogenous factors predisposing to scurvy have been established. The existence of such factors, except those mentioned, must be looked upon as altogether hypothetical.

CHAPTER III.

The latent period of scurvy.

Scorbut gravior has a progressive course from beginning to end. Also scorbut mitior, where the organism receives a certain degree of protective dose, has a progressive course, old tissue being constantly resorbed without being replaced by new of full quality. Even in the latent cases, therefore, the

long bones for instance become more and more brittle. The moment when a latent stage passes into a manifest is for each case determined by the relation between the atrophy of the tissue and the demands made on it. A violent blow may, for instance, by causing a fracture reveal a scurvy which without this accident might still have been latent for a long time. It is the same with a hemorrhage caused by an infectious hyperemia. From this it is obvious that the line of demarcation between latent and manifest scurvy is movable. Most authors also suppose the presence of an intermediary stage between the latent and the distinctly manifest stage. FRAENKEL states that »bei einem nicht geringen Prozentsatz der Fälle welche unter dem Diagnose Darmkatarrh mit Anaemie, Pädatrophy u. dgl. mehr segeln, sich mancher Fall von Barlowscher Krankheit verbirgt». HEUBNER expresses himself to the same purport. EPSTEIN, HESS and also FRANK state that the growing in height is already during this period arrested in children. ARON denies the presence of such an initial stage, but in this he stands alone against KOCH, SCHOEDEL, HART and LESSING, FINKELSTEIN, L. F. MEYER, CHICK and DALYELL, the above-mentioned authors and all other investigators of mark who have written on the subject.

If thus the supposition of a clinical stage, during which the diagnosis of scurvy often can be made only for the therapeutic effect of antiscorbutics, seems to be well founded, my research has afforded the possibility of understanding this better. Not only in the teeth and the bone-system, but also in muscles, liver, spleen, kidney, salivary gland, adrenal, and probably in other organs, already in the latent stage more or less severe changes appear, which together constitute the scorbutic atrophy of the organism. This atrophy is progressive and gives manifest symptoms after a length of time that varies for the different cases.

The duration of the latent period thus bears a relation first to the antiscorbutic dose given and then also to outward circumstances. In guinea-pigs the latent period is, approximately, with no antiscorbutic 1 week, with 0.1 of the minimum

protective dose more than 2 weeks, with 0.2 m. pr. d. more than 3 weeks, with 0.3 m. pr. d. about 10 weeks, a. s. o. When the dosage of antiscorbutic approaches the completely protective dose, marked clinical symptoms never appear, only indistinct signs of general ill-health. Indeed, I think it very probable that there is a stage of scurvy, when not even patho-anatomically any pathognomonic changes are demonstrable in the teeth, but when nevertheless the promptness with which the vital functions of the body take place is lowered, a scorbut initialis or functional scurvy. ZILVA argues in the same direction.

HESS writes: »There is no doubt a considerable number of infants, who quite unknown to any one pass through the state of latent scurvy. If this large group of cases were included in the incidence of infantile scurvy, we should not look upon it as a disorder, which occurs rarely during the first six months of life.» However, it is probably the same also with other ages in districts, where during certain periods there is only a limited supply of foodstuffs, valuable from the antiscorbutic point of view. In such places scurvy may therefore have a room in the discussion concerning the pathogenesis of diseases of the different organs.

Among subjects already dealt with I refer to the question about the relation of scurvy to the infections, p. 120, heart weakness, p. 81, renal calculi, p. 98, liver changes, p. 89. KOSSLER has in 1922 communicated a case where a patient, treated for a digestive disorder with so-called »lenient» dietary, himself out of nervousness limited it still more, whereupon a manifest scurvy set in. Such cases are probably not unfrequent. The question is whether in this case a latent scurvy, caused by the physician, was not already present.¹ Now, earlier authors², as well as the present writer, have in scorbutic guinea-pigs stated the presence of ulcers in the ventricle or the duodenum. These ulcers are in the duodenum placed above the papilla Vateri

¹ In the case of CORDIER, reported the same year, medical advice regarding dietary had caused *manifest* scurvy.

² The criticism on p. 101, applies to McCarrison's statements in this matter.

and a strong congestive hyperemia is common in this place. One might think of the influence of the acid gastric juice on an atrophic intestinal epithelium, perhaps with a complicating infection. HERZOG presupposes a hemorrhage to be the cause. In any case it is highly important that so-called ulcus-dietary, as well as other »lenient» dietaries, should contain a sufficient dose of antiscorbutic, which surely is often not the case.

It is of the greatest importance to find a test, by which the presence of latent scurvy can be established. Among those indicated for the diagnosis of scurvy by other authors, Roentgen examination of the epiphyses of the long bones, according to FRAENKEL, or of the heart, according to HESS, may be taken into consideration, but these examinations may even in the manifest stage give uncertain results. It seems to me as if the changes in the teeth with atrophy of the processes of the odontoblasts in the dentin, or the precipitate calcium excretion through the urine in the latent stage might be used for creating a method of diagnosing latent scurvy. Experiments in this direction are in progress.

CHAPTER IV.

The calcium metabolism in scurvy.

HESS summarizes the few and partially conflicting examinations of the metabolism in scurvy thus: »The only point in which they agree, is that during the manifest stage the calcium balance is positive.»

Howe and TOVERUD look upon scurvy as a disturbance in the calcium metabolism. Howe writes in 1921: »In calcium disturbances of this kind, two things are to be considered: first, a sufficient supply of calcium and, second, the necessary elements for inducing the fixation of the calcium. The fixation seems to be governed by the vitamine content of the diet.» Thus, Howe and Toverud have a conception of scurvy, which corresponds to that generally prevailing in regard to rickets.

My histological examinations give no reason to suppose that the calcium metabolism is primarily disarranged in scurvy.

On the other hand conclusions may be drawn from the pictures which are highly interesting for explaining the secondary changes which the calcium excretion undergoes in scurvy. In early stages of scurvy a bone is formed which is calcified, but quantitatively as well as qualitatively inferior. The resorption of the old bone seems to proceed normally. The new bone is of small scale and cannot absorb the quantity of calcium made free from the old bone. There ensues in the body a surplus of calcium, and a precipitate excretion takes place, to which the pictures I have found in the kidney in cases of scorbut latens and scorbut mitior bear witness. Afterwards, in the progress of the scurvy a circumstance arises which acts in the opposite direction. Different parenchymatous organs get more and more atrophic and necrotize partially. Dying tissue generally has greater affinity to calcium and thus we see in scorbutic guinea-pigs calcifications appear to a large extent in different organs, principally muscles and liver. This may explain the calcium balance being positive during this stage. In healing, again a strong excretion sets in, which has been noted by several investigators.

This interpretation of the calcium metabolism in scurvy as dependent on different factors has already been sketched in its outlines by GERSTENBERGER. It well agrees with the results gained by LUST and KLOCMANN, BAHRDT and EDELSTEIN, MARIA FRANK (1920).

BAHRDT and EDELSTEIN found considerably diminished calcium and phosphorus contents in bones and muscles of a scorbutic infant. The elements in question were diminished in about the same percentage as the total ash. This discovery is not unexpected where a protic bone is concerned. Bahrdt and Edelstein are of opinion that it is absolutely contrary to the result of Lust and Klocmann who found a positive calcium balance in florid scurvy, but a negative balance during the healing stage. These apparently opposite results are explicable if we bear in mind that Bahrdt and Edelstein's children had manifest scurvy since at least six weeks back, those of Lust and Klocmann since at least four months.

HOWARD and INGVALDSEN found calcium to be retained during manifest scurvy, but the less, the more the disease proceeded. It is open to doubt, however, whether condensed milk as only diet calls forth simple scurvy in monkey. It is probable that in this food also other necessary substances beside the antiscorbutic are lacking.

MOREL etc. examined the ash and calcium contents in the bones of ten scorbutic guinea-pigs, without further indicating which bones, and stated values fully comparable to those of the control animals. As the calcium contents of the bone *a priori* may be supposed to be diminished in the osteoporotic diaphysis but increased in the epiphysis with its shapeless masses of calcium columns, it is necessary to state clearly from where the examined piece of bone is taken.

PITZ' experiments, like others where no importance has been attached to the quantity of fresh milk consumed, can not be taken into consideration.

ROBB etc. have in 1921 published experiments aimed to elucidate the calcium metabolism in scorbutic guinea-pigs. The arrangement of the experiment with use of calcium-free diet etc. is so unsuitable for the purpose, the judgment of the experimental figures so uncritical, that no notice can be taken of the conclusions.¹

CHAPTER V.

Scurvy and rickets.

The differences recorded by previous investigators between the bone pictures in scurvy and in rickets have been established by my investigations. Only in one respect, the initial hyperemia, I have found these changes agreeing. Moreover, in scurvy this hyperemia soon gives place in the metaphyses of the long bones to a tissue containing very few vessels, the frame-work marrow. The most pronounced difference between

¹ IWABUCHI found in 1922 no noteworthy changes from the normal of the calcium contents of bones, muscles, liver, spleen, in guinea-pigs with scorbut mitior manifestus, 36—46 days.

scurvy and rickets in the bone-system is their relation to the calcification. In rickets, an osteoid substance is formed, which is not calcified. In scurvy, a bone is formed to a limited extent, which is rapidly calcified. The histological picture gives the differential diagnosis as well as the Roentgen picture (FRAENKEL, HOFFMANN). Already macroscopically, the easily breaking, brittle and light scorbutic bone differs from the flexible, heavy rachitic bone. A real difficulty in distinguishing them only occurs when it is a question of healing rickets. Clinically, a scorbutic and a rachitic rosary may be impossible to distinguish from each other. Other findings will then have to decide the diagnosis.

Through the description, quoted on p. 203, of the bone changes in a child with coincident scurvy and rickets, Quensel has shown how the shares of both diseases in the bone picture may be distinguished, a problem which Schoedel has designated as difficult, if not impossible, to solve.

CHAPTER VI.

Scurvy and inanition.

The question how far the scorbutic changes and symptoms might be consequences of inanition has been examined by several investigators from HOLST and FRÖLICH to COHEN and MENDEL. All of them arrive at a conclusion agreeing with that of the two last-named authors, that »the inanition is a result of the scorbutic symptoms rather than a forerunner of them». The latest to write on this matter are MOURIQUAND and MICHEL: »Le scorbut et l'inanition sont deux faits absolument distincts. Nous estimons que l'apparition des symptômes de scorbut n'a aucun rapport précis avec l'inanition et que cette dernière ne constitue pour eux qu'un épiphénomène généralement tardif.» On the whole the study of my 4 animals, which have been put on relative general inanition but have received a sufficient protective dose of antiscorbutic, has given a concordant result. The animals died after one to two weeks

and showed at the death no trace of the changes of teeth or bones which have been described as scorbutic. In the skeleton muscles, heart, liver, spleen, kidneys, salivary glands, adrenals, of the inanition animals there are light atrophic changes resembling those described in scurvy. It can not be excluded that the inanition has contributed to these changes in certain among the scorbutic animals. In others among these, where there has been no decrease of weight, this is probably excluded. The possible inanition which may have been prevailing during the last days is not sufficient alone to explain these changes in the parenchymatous organs of the scorbutic animals. The difference in degree between the changes in the inanition animals and those with scurvy is too great for that. In the chapter on Pathogenesis I have set forth that I look upon the atrophic changes in animals upon different deficiency diets as similar but not identical.

CHAPTER VII.

A modified method for experimental rating of the antiscorbutic value.

The method for testing the antiscorbutic value of a substance which has up till now been most frequently employed is to determine the minimum protective dose on guinea-pigs. The experimental period has generally been fixed at 90 days, »after which time it is unlikely that death from scurvy will occur» (SHERMAN etc.). MOURIQUAND and MICHEL claim, however, that the animals should live 150 days and more, as they have seen a latent scurvy become manifest as late as that with a constant antiscorbutic dose. Neither the French, nor the American authors say anything about a microscopical examination of the experimental animal.

SHERMAN, LA MER and CAMPBELL point out that if in a certain quantity of a juice, that has been tested with regard to its antiscorbutic value, there is not enough for complete pro-

tection, it is still possible to judge the relative quantity of antiscorbutic administered through comparing the weight curves, survival periods, severity of the symptoms, and autopsy findings for the animals examined with a standard scale. »Thus, one is not confined entirely to a comparison of the so-called minimum protective doses, since the quantitative rating of the degree of protection afforded permits comparisons to be made upon animals receiving less than the amount required for complete protection.» For this a reliable scale of comparison is required. Sherman etc. communicate one. My experiments give another, somewhat different. The origin of the difference is that Sherman etc. do not seem to undertake a microscopic examination in this connection, and thus their minimum protective dose means a dose which protects from changes enough marked to be observed macroscopically at the *post-mortem* examination. As I have proved, a dose twice as large as this is necessary to prevent anatomical changes in the teeth. In my opinion it is to be preferred, by »protective dose» to mean a *fully* protective dose, and in order to establish this amount a histological examination of the teeth is necessary. Of course, the method employed by Sherman etc. is also practicable although somewhat uncertain, if only in every case it is indicated how the experiment has been made.

The early, marked and pathognomonic changes in the teeth of guinea-pigs, which we have described, permit a modification of the indicated methods. After some animals (weight not much above 300 grams) have received a certain quantity of the substance, the antiscorbutic value of which is to be tested, during 2 weeks, they are killed. The lower jaw is decalcified and a cross section of the incisor root is examined in the manner described in the chapter on »Teeth» p. 40. A completely protective dose gives a picture like that in Fig. 30. Smaller doses may to a certain extent be rated by a method analogous to that of Sherman etc., described above, whereby Fig. 22—29 may serve as scale of comparison. *By means of this method, the antiscorbutic value of a product can be tested in three weeks instead of three months.*

CHAPTER VIII.

Pathogenesis of scurvy. Relation of scurvy to other deficiency diseases.

»Viewing the situation broadly, it must be acknowledged that, except for the realization that scurvy is due to a new food factor, a vitamin, our fundamental understanding of its pathogenesis has advanced but little» (HESS 1920). ASCHOFF and KOCH presume »eine kolloid-chemische Umstimmung des Blutes oder der Gefäßwände» with »eine fehlende oder schlechte Bildung von Kittsubstanzen, durch deren Mangel die Osteoblasten zur Untätigkeit bestimmt werden und keinen Anreiz zur Neubildung erhalten». From different quarters (MELLANBY, BRODERICH, TAYLOR, quoted after ORBAN) the supposition has been brought forth, in accordance with McCarrison's investigation, that the antiscorbutic substance would exercise its influence through the organs of internal secretion. The universal opinion is expressed by BERG 1922 thus: »Wie man die Haupterscheinungen, die wir als teilweise Decomposition bezeichnen könnten, einheitlich aus einem Gesichtspunkte aus erklären soll, bleibt vorläufig ganz rätselhaft».

Two pathogenetic problems have up till now been placed in the foreground for the study of scurvy. The first is this: In which ways does the antiscorbutic influence the osteoblasts and vascular walls, directly or by the means of other organs (glands, endothelial cells)? The second problem is: How does the antiscorbutic exercise its effect, by itself entering the products formed or by rendering certain reactions possible without itself being destroyed?

The present investigation widens the first question. It has been established that the antiscorbutic is necessary to continued activity and life of various more highly differentiated cells in vivid activity, odontoblasts, osteoblasts, chondroblasts, fibroblasts, lymphoblasts, the muscle cells, and the parenchymatous cells of the liver, salivary gland, adrenal and kidney.

All these cells seem, in the absence or deficiency of antiscorbutic, to be subject to atrophy and yield a product which is quantitatively as well as qualitatively inferior. The smaller this insufficient dose of antiscorbutic, the less developed the appearance of these cells and of their products (proved with regard to odontoblasts, osteoblasts and fibroblasts; to be presumed in the rest). If antiscorbutic is altogether lacking in the food, these cells go on living for a certain time and yield during this time products, which deteriorate day by day till the activity is completely arrested and the death of the cell ensues.

HESS says in his chapter on symptomatology: »Scurvy reduces the nutritional state of probably all the cells and tissues of the body.» Even if this is presumable, I would like, in accordance with my investigations, for the time being to formulate this sentence thus: Scurvy reduces the nutritional state and the active function of probably all the most active, most rapidly growing and highest differentiated cells of the body. This reduction begins with the absence of antiscorbutic in the food. It becomes manifest at a rate that varies for the different cells and tissues: first in odontoblasts, then in osteoblasts, muscle cells, lymphoid tissue, fibroblasts, and salivary glands, then in the liver, adrenal, chondroblasts, and last in the epithelium of the kidney. The order in which the changes set in and continue in odontoblasts, osteoblasts and chondroblasts seems to argue for the notion that phylogenetically older and histo-functionally less differentiated cells are later and more lightly struck by the deficiency of antiscorbutic.

The conformity which from a purely histological point of view is found with regard to the cell changes (*cf.*, for instance, hyperemia, the initial disarrangement with disintegration of the gradually lowering cell layer as to odontoblasts and chondroblasts) seems to indicate that antiscorbutic has a similar effect on different cells. It seems to me most probable that this effect is exercised directly on the cells by the antiscorbutic which has passed into the blood. In any case, after my investigation the statement of LUBARSCH still holds true: »Eine

besondere Beteiligung der innersekretorischen Organe bei (der Pathogenese der) Unterernährungskrankheiten ist bisher weder experimentell noch bei Menschen nachgewiesen».

As to the second pathogenetic problem, the inner nature of the influence of antiscorbutic on the cells, my investigation gives no hold. For solving this question special physiological and biochemical experiments are necessary. A few remarks may be made.

ABDERHALDEN and WERTHEIMER have carried out experiments in order to determine the oxygen consumed by different cells under influence of different substances. They also tested various antiscorbutics (juice of lemon, orange, raspberry, maceration of dandelion, sauerkraut, lettuce) and found an increased oxygen consumption in liver, kidney, muscle and lung tissue, and in red blood-corpuses, but not in brain-tissue, when the above-mentioned antiscorbutics were provided. This effect turned out to be parallel with the antiscorbutic value of those substances so that for instance the acid juices preserved their effectiveness after certain heating, while the neutral and alkaline juices lost theirs, a circumstance which might indicate that we have here to deal with an effect of the antiscorbutic on the oxygen consumption of the cells. — In the same year GYÖRGY published similar investigations with similar result. In this matter, on the other hand, we cannot take into account FREUDENBERG's work (also in 1921), as it seems very uncertain whether the extract of carrots («Rubio») which he has used has contained any antiscorbutic at all.

The mentioned investigations, connected with the experiences gained of late years (see p. 12) about the injurious effect on antiscorbutic of oxygenation, and my results as to the necessity of antiscorbutic for getting fully satisfactory products of the cellular activity, suggest the possibility that the antiscorbutic is necessary for the oxydative activity of the cells. According to LOEB the cell nucleus is an organ for this activity. In this connection some of my observations are interesting. First, that in the scorbutic atrophy the nuclei from the outset are highly affected and show degenerative changes

(pyknosis). Further, the special form of nucleus change that is represented by the giant-nuclei cells which appear in the muscles in scurvy as well as in inanition.

The question is open whether the antiscorbutic in its effect on cell processes — the nature of which up to the present is altogether unknown — itself enters wholly or partially the newly formed cell products, or whether it is excreted, more or less inactivated.

As the scorbutic changes in the bones are seen most markedly in the growth zones, scurvy has here the same localization as rickets and lues. VIRCHOW says about this question that »alle Organe zur Zeit ihrer physiologischen Kulmination oder gesteigerten physiologischen Funktion am leichtesten Angriffspunkte für äussere Schädlichkeiten darbieten«. In the matter of scurvy we must look for a special explanation. Its nature is a diminution even until disappearance of the power of the active cells to renew their respective products, and under such circumstances the changes must be expected to appear first of all in the places where the growth and with that also the resorption are most rapid.

The scorbutic changes have hitherto been defined as a failing apposition in a normally continuing resorption. My investigations modify this definition in two respects. According to these investigations the *inability* of apposition is preceded by a stage where there is a *reduced* ability, which results in a quantitatively and qualitatively inferior product. This product will in the course of the disease more rapidly fall a victim to the destroying powers. There does not seem to be any reason for presuming an increase of these destroying factors, as there are no signs of this in the tissue formed before the onset of scurvy.

The interpretation of scurvy as a general, though not uniform, atrophy of the different tissues and organs of the body agrees well with the clinical symptoms. I have not found any symptom, the scorbutic nature of which is probable, that does

not receive its natural explanation through such an interpretation. Among such symptoms may be mentioned:

- 1) The sub- or anacidity in the gastric juice (BIERICH);
- 2) The diminished adrenalin contents in the adrenal (McCARRISON a. o.);
- 3) The failing regeneration of white and red blood-corpules, and their extraordinarily rapid new formation in healing (SALLE and ROSENBERG a. o.);
- 4) The diminishing of the opsonic index (FORTENATO);
- 5) The diminished resistance to infections;
- 6) The appearance of hemorrhages in complications during the convalescence.

This list might be continued to any length. It is of interest to note CRAMER and MOTTRAM's demonstration that certain changes in scurvy — great atrophy of the lymphoid tissue, the thymus, the spleen and the lymphatic glands — can also be brought about through exposure to X-rays.

If the conception of the nature of scurvy which I have arrived at through my studies differs from that prevailing during the last twenty years, yet it does not by any means lack contact with the literature. With regard to the changes in the different organs, this is indicated above in the separate chapters. I will also once more call attention to the statement by HESS, which I have quoted on p. 134. Certain older investigators called their works »De atrophia scorbutico» (MENGERING, 1652). It seems probable that already LINNÉ has observed the calcium deposits in different organs, which have been pointed out by HART and LESSING, then by other authors and are also observed by me. LINNÉ writes in his lectures about 1770: »Thus no materia calculosa arises from fresh fruit. — — — If you go to the butcher's shop in the wintertime, you will certainly see in the animals then killed several signs in liver, heart and lungs of obstructions infallibly arising from dry vegetables which are given them to eat in the winter; but if you go there in the spring and summer when the cattle get green vegetables, you will see that those which are then slaughtered are free from such obstructions».

In order to make clear the relation of scurvy to other deficiency diseases I will dwell upon the appearance of edema in scurvy. Accumulation of liquid in serous cavities and anasarca is often in clinical reports described as a scorbutic symptom. Also in guinea-pigs it is the same, but, as far as I have been able to find, only in cases where the basal diet has not been complete. On the other hand, local edema is often seen in the neighbourhood of large hemorrhages. This edema may be called scorbutic, but it has no *direct* connection with the changes brought about by scurvy in the cells. It is the same with the terminal cardiac edema. NOBEL and WALLGREN, who suppose the presence of an invisible scorbutic edema, attach special importance to the increased quantity of urine, which is found in the beginning of the healing stage. This may be explained, however, without presuming any hidden edema, through the circumstance that when the healing stage sets in, large quantities of dead material from the necrotic tissues are excreted. In any case a scorbutic edema has not yet been proved. Instead it seems probable that the edema present in clinical scurvy ought generally to be placed in connection with the so-called hunger edema (NOEGGERATH etc., IWABUCHI, PRYM, MOURIQUAND etc.). The pathogenesis of this edema has not been made clear. LUBARSCH considers it due to a deficiency of complete albumen, JANSEN a. o. think that the reason is deficient supply of calories with coincident too strong contents of water and salts, other investigators consider vitamin deficiency as an essential factor. It seems certain, however, that the war-edema is caused by deficiency in the food and that it is often clinically found together with other deficiency diseases (beriberi, scurvy).

In the edema disease the main feature of the patho-anatomical picture is an atrophy. It is the same with beriberi, and atrophic features are also seen in other deficiency diseases, as well as in general inanition. Thus several investigators have stated some symptoms to be the same or very nearly the same in beriberi and in scurvy (HESS, DARLING). This is not surprising. STEINITZ and HOPKINS point out that lack of any

substance necessary to a cell leads to the decline and death of the cell, and this applies to the different vitamins as well as to aminoacids and salts. Theoretically, a large number of deficiency diseases are thus to be supposed, besides all intermingling forms, and the symptom which a priori must be expected in these diseases seems to be a more or less general atrophy. That the diseases, which are clinically described as scurvy, beriberi, etc., in reality most frequently are intermingling forms, is probable¹. Nevertheless, they may each in their simple forms have special pathological features, which the experimental research has to make clear. This investigation, which has just only begun, of the different members in the family of the deficiency diseases, will show the way to a better distinction between them than is now possible. In discussing the different clinical symptoms, also those of scurvy, this undecided state of things must be borne in mind (*e. g.* nyctalopia in scurvy, Loewy 1921). In our Northern countries scurvy may require a special interest among the deficiency diseases, as in its latent forms it is the one most probably met with.

In this treatment of the pathogenesis of scurvy, I have presumed its etiology as established, as being a deficiency in the food of a substance or a group of substances with unknown chemical constitution. However, many German authors have even in recent years kept to the conception of scurvy as an infection or toxic disease. I enter into this question to some extent in my chapter on »Scurvy and infection». These hypotheses — for instance, that of toxic products originating from sterilization of milk — which, to put it mildly, may be termed unnecessary, have been exhaustively reported by NOBEL in 1921. He also dwells at some length upon BOLLE's and BARTENSTEIN's unsuccessful attempts at inducing scurvy in guinea-pigs, but only mentions HOLST and FRÖLICH's work cursorily in two lines, thus giving an example of how national points of view may retard the solving of scientific problems.

The risk involved in an adherence to the theory of infec-

¹ For the cases, described in the literature as »scurvy in breast-fed infants», this is recently proved by POGORSCHESKY.

tion and neglect of well established investigation results is strikingly demonstrated by the following example. v. PIRQUET indicates in an essay »Die Aufgaben der Küche» 1918 the task of the kitchen to be to prepare quantitatively determined and according to the economical laws selected articles of food so as to make them 1:0 innocuous, 2:0 digestible, 3:0 palatable. For conserving the milk after boiling he recommends hydrogen peroxid. He thus takes no account of the antiscorbutic value of the food. In 1920, CHICK and DALYELL could prove a latent scurvy among the children at the age of 6—14 in v. Pirquet's clinic, owing to the unsuitable preparation of the fresh vegetables, which were given in a fully sufficient ration (200 grams) but were made less valuable as antiscorbutic through the manner of cooking. When this ration had to be reduced to 70 grams, a scurvy epidemic broke out as early as after 8 weeks.

Summary and conclusions of Parts II and III.

The patho-anatomical changes in scurvy have at a closer study been found to be much more widely spread than has been supposed up till now. Such changes have been recognized in all tissues and organs, where the different stages of scurvy were examined. With regard to the bone formation which earlier has been of central interest to investigators, the experiments have established the presence of a hitherto generally neglected stage, before all bone formation ceases. During this stage, which either appears as a period in the development of scurvy, when there is no antiscorbutic in the food, or, with a certain but insufficient dose, represents the definite picture of the disease, the bone-building cells, odontoblasts and osteoblasts, seem to lose more and more of their typical appearance, and the product they yield to diverge more and more from the normal. It seems to be a lowering of dignity, the degree of which is directly determined by the antiscorbutic dose. The characteristics of this scorbutic bone of lower quality, which has been observed by earlier investigators but

generally been misinterpreted, are described for teeth, endosomal and enchondral bone formation. For the connective tissue a general atrophy is described, which especially overtakes the collagen fibrils. This change is also proved in the vascular walls. In muscles, lymphoid tissue, liver, salivary gland, adrenal and kidney an atrophy combined with necrosis has been found. Also in these regions the tissues seem more severely struck, the more the scurvy is developed. It is established that some of the most active and most differentiated of the cells in the body are caught earliest and most severely by the scorbutic atrophy. The changes which have been described may be traced at a very early stage of the latent period. The importance of subjecting this latent stage to a close study is strongly emphasized.

Through these investigations the pathological picture of scurvy has thus been amplified, and the principal features of the disease have been analysed and found to be uniformly explainable.

PART IV.

Scurvy and tuberculosis.

CHAPTER I.

Historical review.

An importance of the diet to the progress of tuberculosis has been assumed already by LINNÉ. He writes in 1766: »Ingesta nimis nutrantia — nonne hinc saepissime oritur Phtisis juvenum?» On the contrary, subsequent investigators have as a rule regarded the general malnutrition as acting upon the progress of tuberculosis, though the problem up till the present time has evoked a comparatively small interest. CORNET and KOSSEL write in 1913: »Es ist wohl denkbar, dass ein abgekapselter Herd durch Unterernährung ausgelaugt und die Bacillen mobilisiert werden». The authors are evidently thinking of the theory of »demineralisation». LÖWENSTEIN, who in the

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